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Student Leadership Styles in a Teacher's College

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Abstract: As the demands on college students grow, effective leadership within educational institutions is becoming increasingly essential. This qualitative study uses Goleman's Leadership Styles framework to examine the leadership styles of nine chairpersons from various student organisations within a teacher's college. Through purposeful sampling and semi-structured interviews, the study identified 13 leadership approaches: Visionary, Decisive, Straightforward, Mandating, Role Model, Connected, Empathetic, Reflective, Collaborative, Engaged, Supportive, Effective Communicator, and Mindful. These styles illustrate how student leaders manage their organisations effectively. The findings suggest that understanding these leadership styles can help educational institutions foster more effective leadership, enhance organisational performance, and align leadership training with student needs.

Keywords: Student Leader, Leadership Styles, Student Leadership Styles, Teacher's College

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1.1 Introduction

Leadership is a critical factor in the success of any organisation, as it involves influencing followers to achieve common goals (Noori, 2021; Al Khajeh, 2018). The leadership style adopted by an organisation significantly affects its outcomes, making it essential for success (Al Khajeh, 2018). Leadership style is defined by a combination of traits and behaviours that leaders employ when interacting with their teams, influencing overall performance (Mitonga-Monga & Coetzee, 2012).

In educational institutions, student leadership becomes increasingly vital, as it involves the active engagement of students in their educational processes and the development of essential skills (Building Student Leadership in the

Classroom, 2023). As Kumaku (2021) highlighted, student leaders are crucial in managing educational institutions. The importance of student leadership in shaping campus culture, fostering engagement, and nurturing future leaders has been increasingly recognised (Rodriguez & Villareal, 2003; Skalicky et al., 2020). Identifying these leadership styles is vital, as it enhances student involvement and decision-making and promotes a supportive learning environment, ultimately contributing to the institution's success (Rodriguez & Villareal, 2003).

This study identifies and analyses the prevalent leadership styles among student leaders in a teacher's college. To achieve these aims, it will examine the leadership styles of nine chairpersons from various organisations within the College of Education at a public university, drawing on Goleman's Leadership Styles Theory (2002). Goleman's framework defines six distinct leadership styles: authoritative, commanding, pacesetter, affiliative, democratic, and coaching.

The findings of this research hold significance for various stakeholders: (1) Student leaders can benefit from understanding their leadership styles, enabling self-assessment and effectiveness in achieving organisational goals. (2) Universities can adjust their projects and activities based on awareness of student leaders' styles. (3) The student body can identify effective leaders and suitable leadership styles through the practices of their peers.

2.1 Methods

Research design

This study employed a qualitative research design to explore the leadership styles of student leaders in a teacher's college. The study aligns with the Constructionism epistemology, which posits that knowledge is constructed through experiences (Papert, 1991). This epistemology is particularly relevant as it emphasises the importance of understanding how student leaders develop and express their leadership identities within their educational context.

The research utilises a narrative inquiry approach, relying on stories as the primary data source. This methodology involves collecting narratives from student leaders through semi-structured interviews, allowing them to describe their unique experiences. Such stories reveal the complexities of their identities and leadership styles (Butina, 2015). This approach provides rich, qualitative data that enhances our understanding of how student leaders navigate their roles within educational organisations.

Informants

This study was conducted by nine (9) informants, the Chairpersons of organisations from the College of Education of a public university, each meeting specific inclusion criteria. To be eligible for participation, informants had to be currently enrolled college students within the College of Education, hold the position of Chairperson of one recognised organisation within the college and must have at least three (3) years of service from their respective organisations. The organisations represented in this study were the Associations of General Education Students (AGES), Special Education Students Association (SPEDSA), Kapisanang Diwa at Panitikan (KADIPAN), Science Teachers Major Association (STEMA), Social Science Students Society (3s'), Major of Values Education (MOVE), Association of Early Childhood Education Students (AECES), Circle of Mathematicians (COM), and English Major's Organization (EMO). The final sample size was nine informants. By drawing on the unique perspectives of these individuals, this study aims to provide valuable insights into the topic under investigation.

Figure 1. Profile of the Informant Instrument

Pseudonyms of Informant	Age	Organisation	Years of Service
Lela	21	AGES	3
Rmellah	20	SPEDSA	3
Jerol	20	KADIPAN	3
Axl	23	STEMA	4
Lex	23	3S' SOCIETY	4
Krexie	21	MOVE	3
Renee	20	AECES	3
Stephen	23	COM	4
Pat	21	EMO	3

A student leadership style interview guide – a researcher-made interview guide duly validated by experts in qualitative research – anchored with Goleman’s Leadership Styles theory (2002) will be used to investigate students' leadership styles to explore their practices and behaviour in handling their respective organisations. The questionnaire is divided into two parts: Part I gathers demographic information to understand better the informant’s background and eligibility to participate, while Part II consists of a series of questions that aim to extract information about the student leader's leadership practices and determine their leadership style.

The researchers took several measures to increase the study's accuracy and credibility. They provided the informants with information about the research to verify the findings, maintained detailed notes to detect any response variations, and conducted repeated interviews to avoid biases. Furthermore, they used member checks to ensure consistent interpretation of the data and gave informants feedback on the study's conclusions to confirm accuracy.

Data collection

The researchers sent consent letters to the chosen informants to notify them and confirm their participation. Then, the researchers conducted face-to-face interviews with the informants, giving them ample time to answer the questionnaire. After that, the researchers instructed the informants to return their answered documents to the researchers on or before the provided deadline. To allow researchers to verify the data received, inquire for clarification, and provide additional questions to address the research problem thoroughly, the researchers directly messaged the informants through their Messenger accounts.

'Informed consent' is the basis of ethical study (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011). Informants must be mindful of the inquiries they will be generating, the intentions that the information they provide will serve, and the potential outcomes. The informants require a signed and explicit authorisation to participate in the research, such as comprehending their rights to obtain their data and the right to withdraw their participation at any point during the study. The informants have knowingly and willingly shared the data in a trusting relationship, expecting that it will not be shared with anyone else without their consent unless strictly necessary for the original publicity.

Data analysis

The data collected from the chairpersons of nine (9) organisations under the College of Education was examined and studied by the researchers using qualitative data analysis techniques. A method for qualitative data interpretation

known as thematic analysis identifies patterns in the data. Responding to the research questions formed the basis of the procedure. Caulfield's (2022) thematic analysis includes thoroughly reviewing the data, coding and segmenting it into sections, and using the codes to produce themes. Researchers can define and conclude. The data is then organised into patterns to aid in addressing research questions. Finally, textual representations of the recognised and arranged patterns are presented. This process makes gathering data verification, implications, and conclusions possible. The results demonstrated that the overwhelming majority of respondents supported the proposed changes.

3.1 Results

The data extracted from the informants' transcripts were categorised into thirteen themes based on Goleman's six leadership categories. These themes include Visionary, Decisive, Straightforward, Mandating, Role Model, Connected, Empathetic, Reflective, Collaborative, Engaged, Supportive, Effective Communicator, and Mindful. Each theme is divided into subcategories to provide in-depth insights into the informants' leadership experiences.

Authoritative Leadership

Goleman's authoritative leadership style, often called visionary leadership, is characterised by a leader's ability to provide a clear vision and direction for their team (HRDQ, 2022). This style is particularly effective when a team is uncertain or navigating new situations. The data from informants highlighted traits associated with the authoritative style, leading to two subcategories: Visionary and Decisive.

Visionary: Authoritative leaders articulate a compelling vision for the future, inspiring their team to work towards it. They set clear goals and trust their members to take calculated risks to achieve those goals. For example:

Axl: "Clarify my career goals and choose a course of action."

Axl: "Creating a cohesive team committed to working toward a common vision."

Decisive: Authoritative leaders are known for making prompt and resolute decisions. This leadership style is characterised by assertiveness and a clear expectation of compliance. For instance:

Stephen: "I am the one that ultimately makes the final decision in case votation will not suffice."

Renee: "I am the one who initiates group activities... and many more unofficial things."

Commanding Leadership

Commanding leaders are often perceived as direct and authoritative, driven to succeed (Bullwinkle, 2023). Informants displayed traits associated with this style, which is divided into two subcategories: Straightforward and Mandating.

Straightforward: Commanding leaders adopt a direct approach, often asserting control. Their motto is typically "my way or the highway" (Knights, 2022). For example:

Krexie: "I confronted them about their shortcomings."

Mandating: This leadership style enforces strict standards and requires adherence to regulations. Clear goals and expectations characterise it. For example:

Axl: “Frequently challenge them to take more responsibility for their work.” Axl: “Regularly pushing them outside of their comfort zones.”

Pacesetting Leadership

Goleman's pacesetting leadership style involves setting high standards and expectations for team performance. Pacesetting leaders lead by example and motivate their teams to meet these expectations (HRDQ, 2022). The findings indicate a connection to the Role Model subcategory.

Role Model: Pacesetting leaders inspire others through their exemplary performance. They work with high levels of efficiency and quality, encouraging their teams to do the same. For example:

Axl: “I always act in the best interests of the entire organisation.” Axl: “I do my best to be a positive role model.”

Affiliative Leadership

According to Goleman's model, affiliative leaders prioritise creating a positive work environment and fostering strong relationships with their team members. This style is particularly effective in improving team morale and motivation. The data from informants revealed traits linked to this style, organised into three subcategories: Connected, Empathetic, and Reflective.

Connected: Affiliative leaders focus on building enduring bonds with their teams. Strong relationships enhance work satisfaction and team dynamics (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978; House & Aditya, 1997). For instance:

Lela: “We have been able to organise activities, and most of all, we feel United despite some officers who cannot fulfil their duties correctly.”

Empathetic: These leaders understand the needs and emotions of their team members, fostering trust and collaboration. For example:

Axl: “I enjoy bringing about positive change among my fellow team members.”

Rmellah: “Giving them hope and reminding them that they are not alone in this journey.”

Reflective: Reflective leaders engage in ongoing personal growth and self-awareness, which enhances their capacity to support their team. For example:

Axl: “It is crucial to avoid growing pessimistic and to continue believing in my ability to effect change for the better.”

Democratic Leadership

Democratic leadership emphasises participation and collaboration in decision-making processes. This leadership style fosters inclusiveness, ensuring that team members feel valued and motivated to contribute to achieving common goals. The results highlighted two key themes associated with democratic leadership: Collaborative and Engaged.

Collaborative: Democratic leaders prioritise relationship-building and teamwork, creating an environment where every team member's contributions are acknowledged. This style encourages collective decision-making and shared responsibility among members. For example:

Stephen: "I encourage participation from all my members and allow them to express their opinions and suggestions."

Krexie: "My way of showing that each member is involved in the decision-making process."

Engaged: Engaged leaders actively involve their team members in discussions and decisions, promoting a sense of ownership and commitment to the organisation's goals. This engagement is crucial for enhancing motivation and fostering a positive team dynamic. For instance:

Axl: "I concentrate my efforts on encouraging our co-members to achieve ever greater goals."

Lela: "We have met different types of people and collaborated with them to bring inclusivity and bridge the gap."

Coaching Leadership

Coaching leaders focus on developing a high-performance culture through partnership and collaboration. They emphasise effective communication and empower team members to make confident decisions (Knights, 2022). Informants identified traits associated with this style, which they categorised into three subcategories: supportive, Effective Communicator, and Mindful.

Supportive: Coaching leaders foster trust through regular engagement and interaction with team members. For example:

Lex: "I am very open in guiding each member and providing feedback."

Effective Communicator: These leaders excel in communication, using it to enhance problem-solving skills. For example:

Stephen: "I believe in fostering a culture of collaboration and open communication."

Mindful: Coaching leaders recognise their influence and strive to create positive outcomes. For example:

Jerol: "Reminded me always to carry on the tradition of excellence."

4.1 Discussion

The findings from this study provide deep insights into the prevalent leadership styles among student leaders in a teacher's college, utilising Goleman's leadership categories as a framework. The results, categorised into thirteen themes, align with Goleman's six primary leadership styles: Authoritative, Commanding, pace-setting, Affiliative, Democratic, and Coaching. Each theme—Visionary, Decisive, Straightforward, Mandating, Role Model, Connected, Empathetic, Reflective, Collaborative, Engaged, Supportive, Effective Communicator, and Mindful —illustrates the diverse approaches that student leaders adopt.

Goleman (2004) highlights how visionary leadership, with its clear articulation of goals and direction, correlates with enhanced organisational performance. This finding aligns with our results, where visionary leaders could inspire their teams by setting clear objectives. Similarly, the importance of emotional intelligence in leadership is a recurring theme in studies like Mitonga-Monga and Coetzee (2012), who found that leaders who foster emotional connections create more cohesive teams. In our study, affiliative leaders, characterised by empathy and connection, contributed significantly to student engagement and organisational unity, consistent with Goleman's findings on the affiliative style.

In contrast, while commanding leadership showed potential in driving results, our study echoed concerns De Hoogh & Hartog (2008) raised regarding its negative consequences. Our informants indicated that while direct and assertive leadership could enforce standards, it often risked alienating team members, especially if not coupled with empathy. This aligns with Lindberg's (2023) analysis, which emphasised that overusing commanding leadership can result in disengagement—a finding mirrored by our data on team member dissatisfaction with overly authoritative approaches.

Similarly, pacesetter leadership, as observed in our findings, demands high standards but at the cost of potential burnout among members. This mirrors findings from studies like HRDQ (2022), which highlighted that pacesetter leaders, although motivating, often push their teams too hard, leading to disengagement. Our research adds to this by showcasing how student leaders struggle with these high expectations, often resulting in stress and decreased performance, a sentiment shared in Pedrosa's (2023) work on student burnout.

This study contributes uniquely to the existing body of knowledge by highlighting the importance of flexibility in leadership styles within an educational setting. Unlike previous research, which often emphasised the dominance of one style, our findings suggest that effective student leadership relies on a blend of multiple styles. For instance, while visionary and democratic leadership fostered inclusiveness and motivation, more rigid styles like commanding and pacesetter had mixed outcomes, mainly when applied without balancing emotional intelligence or support.

5.1 Conclusion

Effective leadership in educational settings requires flexibility and a keen understanding of when to employ different styles to inspire and engage peers. Each style contributes uniquely to team dynamics and overall organisational success. Visionary and democratic leadership styles can foster an inclusive atmosphere that enhances collaboration and motivates students to take ownership of their roles, whereas commanding styles can ensure clarity, accountability, and immediate results when needed. These styles often lead to stress, burnout, and disengagement if not balanced with empathy and support.

Institutions should invest in leadership development programs that enhance individual leadership skills and encourage the integration of multiple styles. This approach fosters an environment where students feel empowered to lead effectively, enhancing their academic performance and engagement.

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